

LINGUISTIC THEORY ON CHARACTERISTICS OF ENGLISH PHRASEOLOGY AND IDIOMATICITY

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Phraseology studies collocations of words (phraseologisms, phraseological units, idioms), where the meaning of the whole collocation is different from the simple sum of literal meanings of the words, comprising a phraseological unit. For example, ‘The Dutch auction’ is not an auction taking place in the Netherlands. The meaning of this phraseological unit refers to any auction, where instead of rising, the prices fall (compare “Dutch comfort”, “Dutch courage”, “Dutch treat” reflecting complicated historical factors). Phraseological units are stable word groups with partially or fully transferred meanings ("to kick the bucket", “Greek gift”, “drink till all's blue”, “drunk as a fiddler (drunk as a lord, as a boiled owl)”, “as mad as a hatter (as a march hare)”).¹

Opinions differ as to how the phraseological units should be defined, classified, described, and analyzed. To make matters worse, no two authors agree on the terminology they use. The word "phraseology", for instance, has very different meanings in different countries. In Russian linguistics literature, the term has come to be used for the whole ensemble of expressions where the meaning of one element is dependent on the other, irrespective of the structure and properties of the unit;² with other authors, it denotes only such set expressions which, as distinguished from idioms, do not possess expressiveness or emotional colouring, and also vice versa: only those that are imaginative, expressive and emotional.³ O. S. Ahmanova has repeatedly insisted on the semantic integrity of such phrases

¹ А. В. Кунин, Английская фразеология. М., 1970.стр 54

² А. И. Смирницкий, Лексикология английского языка, М., 1956,

³ В. В. Виноградов, Основные понятия русской фразеологии, Труды юбилейно) научной сессии ЛГУ, Л., 1946;

prevailing over the structural separateness of their elements.⁴ A. V. Koonin lays stress on the structural separateness of the elements in a phraseological unit, on the change of meaning in the whole as compared with its elements taken separately, and on certain minimum stability.

All these authors use the same word "phraseology" to denote the branch of linguistics studying the word groups they have in mind.

In English and American linguistics, the situation is very different. No special branch of study exists and the term "phraseology" is a stylistic one, meaning 'mode of expression, peculiarities of diction, i.e. choice and arrangement of words and phrases characteristic of some author or some literary work.'⁵

The word "idiom" is even more polysemantic. The English use it to denote a mode of expression peculiar to a language, without differentiating between the grammatical and lexical levels; "the syntactical or structural form peculiar to a given language". It may also mean a group of words whose meaning is difficult or impossible to understand from the knowledge of the words considered separately. Moreover, "idiom" may be synonymous with the words "language" or "dialect", denoting a form of expression peculiar to a people, a country, a district, or to one individual. There seems to be no point in enumerating further possibilities. The word "phrase" is no less polysemantic. The term "set expression" is on the contrary more definite and self-explanatory because the first element points out the most important characteristic of these units, namely, their stability, their fixed and ready-made nature. The word "expression" suits our purpose because it is a general term including words, groups of words, and sentences, so that both give up and that's a *horse of another colour*— are expressions. That is why in the

⁴ О. С. Ахманова и Э. М. Медникова, Глобальность номинации как основной признак фразеологической единицы. Сборник «Проблемы устойчивости и вариативности фразеологических единиц», Тула, 1968.

⁵ Webster's Third New International Dictionary of the English Language, G. & C. Merriam Co., Springfield, Massachusetts, 1961.

present chapter we shall use this term in preference of all the others.

Many various lines of approach have been used, and yet the place of set expressions in the vocabulary and the boundaries of this level is one of the great controversial issues of present-day linguistics.

English and American scholars treat set expressions mostly as a problem of applied linguistics, they have concentrated their efforts on compiling dictionaries of idiomatic phrases.⁶ Their object in so doing is chiefly practical: they furnish anyone, native or foreigner, with a guide to colloquial phrases, considering them an important characteristic feature of natural spoken English and a stumbling block for foreigners. The approach is partly didactic, partly stylistic.

The English and the Americans can be proud of a very rich set of dictionaries of word-groups belonging to this type, but the most essential theoretical problems remain not only unsolved but untacked, except for some short notes in works on general linguistics.

Some interesting definitions are achieved in machine translation linguistics. Another important and so far unsolved problem is the question of classification. More or less detailed groupings are given in the books on English idioms by L. P. Smith and W. Ball.⁷ Yet even the authors themselves do not claim that their groupings should be regarded as classifications. They just collect set expressions, explain them, describe some of their peculiarities, such as alliteration, rhyme, contrast, and so on, treating these as devices assuring expressiveness. They also show interest in the origin and etymology of English phrases and arrange them

⁶ The best –known are: V. H. Collins, *A Book of English Idioms with Explanations*, London — New York — Toronto, 1958; J. M. Dixon, *English Idioms*, London, 1927; F. Freeman, *A Concise Dictionary of English Idioms*, London, 1951; Th. R.G. Lyell, *Slang, Phrase and Idiom in Colloquial English and Their Use*, Tokyo, 1931; W. McMordie, *English Idioms and How to Use Them*, Oxford, 1945 (first ed. 1923); L. P. Smith, *Words and Idioms*, London, 1925; Л. П. Смит, *Фразеология английского языка*, М., 1959.

⁷ L. P. Smith and W. Ball “English idioms”. New York — Toronto, 1958

accordingly into phrases from sea life, from agriculture, from hunting, from sports, and so on. The richness of language material makes these practical manuals of everyday phrases very valuable for those interested in learning or teaching English.

A typical example of a fusion is the emotional colloquial expression *as mad as a hatter* 'utterly mad'. Its meaning is not explicable from the meaning of its component parts. When the general phrase is understood, but the meaning of the separate elements is forgotten, misunderstanding of the elements may arise and lead to some transformation. The history of the expression shows that it has nothing to do with the makers or sellers of hats, but really is a reference to a snake (an adder), while mad originally had one of its older meanings 'furious with anger', so that the original meaning was 'as furious as a snake'. Phraseological fusions are specific for every language and do not lend themselves to literal translation into other languages.

Phraseological unities are much more numerous. The emotional quality is based upon the metaphorical image created by the whole as in *to stand (or stick) to one's guns*, i.e. 'refuse to change one's statements or opinions in the face of opposition', implying courage and integrity. The above example reveals another characteristic of the type, namely the possibility of synonymic substitution, which can be only very limited without changing the meaning of the whole. Some of these are easily translated and even international: e.g. *to know the way the wind blows*, *знать куда ветер дует*.

The weak points of this classification have been criticized by several authors.⁸ Trying to apply it to English material, as it has been too often done, one must be aware of its limitations. First, it is next to impossible to say whether a set

⁸ Н. Н. Амосова, Основы английской фразеологии, стр. 6—9. А. В. Кунин, Английская фразеология, М., 1970, стр. 8—9.

expression is demotivated for the speaker or not, as no rigorous criteria exist and no consistent procedures are offered. Secondly, the group of phraseological unities is heterogenous. V. V. Vinogradov makes it include proverbs, two-member technical terms and stereotyped combinations showing no contextual change of meaning whatever. Last but not least, the classification lacks a general theoretical basis, and being developed for the Russian phraseology, does not fit the specifically English features.

Some phraseological units are likened to compound words, others to derivatives. Thus, *to take the chair*—a two-summit unit (there may be units having several summits) is like a compound, whereas, *to give up*—a one-summit unit, is compared to a derivative.

The verb-adverb combinations of the give up or make out (V+adv) type are the most typical one-summit units' characteristic of the present-day English.

Another type of one-summit verbal units are the combinations like to be tired, to be surprised (to be+adj type). The semantical centre here does not coincide with the grammatical one, being transferred to the second component.

Prep+N, prep+N+prep, prep+A, prep+N+conj types are nearer to words and as a rule function in speech as adverbs: by heart, for good, or as form words: by means of, in order that. The units of this group have no semantical centre whatever. Establishing this class of one-summit units A. I. Smirnitsky finds a place for units that have been for a long time the object of many discussions, do not fit into any system, and so are always treated as some sort of exception.

N. N. Amosova defines phraseological units as units of fixed context, and considers the branch of linguistics studying it a separate independent science. Fixed context is defined as a context characterized by a specific and unchanging sequence of definite lexical components, and a peculiar semantic relationship between these. Units of fixed context are subdivided into two types called phrasemes and idioms.

Phrasemes are always binary, e.g. *in to grind one's teeth*, one of the components (*to grind*) has a phraseologically bound meaning, the other (*one's teeth*) serves as the determining context: *to knit one's brows, small hours, small talk, beef tea, husband's tea*.

The other type, i.e. idioms, differs from phrasemes because they cannot be separated into determining context and components with phraseologically bound meaning. The new meaning, the meaning of the idiom, is created by the unit as a whole though every element keeps its usual value, e.g. a mare's nest 'nonsense, a discovery which exists only in the imagination of the finder'. A mare 'a female horse' has obviously no nest. The word mare is monosemantic, and so does not need any determining context. The word nest is polysemantic; besides its main meaning 'the place made by birds for laying eggs and sheltering their young', it may also mean by metonymy 'a brood' or metaphorically 'lodging' and 'bed' and even 'haunt of robbers', etc. None of these, however, is connected with the word mare and they do not occur together in a free phrase. Thus both words keep their usual meanings while the combination as a whole possesses a special meaning.

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